

A New Self-consistent Method for Calculating Chemical Hardness and other Energy Derivatives

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A quadratic Euler-Lagrange equation has been solved for calculating the atomic hardness using the equality of the electrostatic potential at the covalent radius with the chemical potential. A new chemical property, viz. the colour of an atom or a molecule, has been introduced. This helps in understanding how hardness changes if an electron is added to or removed from an atom or a molecule.

Electronegativity¹ and hardness² have been found to be two important concepts in qualitative description of any chemical system. Density functional theory (DFT) has been successful in providing rigorous definitions for these quantities. For an N-electron system the electronegativity (χ) is defined as³

$$\chi = -\mu = - \left(\frac{\partial E}{\partial N} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{v}(r)$, μ and E are external and chemical potentials and energy of the system respectively. For the same system the hardness (η) is given by the corresponding second derivative⁴, viz.

$$\begin{aligned} \eta &= \left(\frac{\partial^2 E}{\partial N^2} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} = - \left(\frac{\partial \chi}{\partial N} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial \mu}{\partial N} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In DFT⁵, μ appears as a Lagrange multiplier in the Euler-Lagrange equation (ELE),

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \rho} = \mu \quad (3)$$

where, ρ is the single-particle density. The ELE takes the following quadratic form if one uses a first-gradient corrected Thomas-Fermi kinetic energy functional^{6,7},

$$ax^2 + bx + c = 0 \quad (4a)$$

where,

$$\tau = \rho^{1/3}, \quad a = -\frac{5}{3} C_k r, \quad b = \frac{4}{3} C_x r \quad (4b)$$

$$c = \frac{9 \times 0.18}{40} \frac{1}{r} - \phi(\mathbf{r}) + \mu r - r \frac{\delta E_c[\rho]}{\delta \rho} \quad (4c)$$

$$\frac{\delta E_c[\rho]}{\delta \rho} = - \frac{9.81 + 28.583 \rho^{-1/3}}{(9.81 + 21.437 \rho^{-1/3})^2} \quad (4d)$$

In equations (4a-d), C_k , C_x and $E_c[\rho]$ are Thomas-Fermi constant, Dirac constant and a correlation

energy functional⁸ respectively. The numerical factor, $9 \times 0.18/40$, in equation (4c) gives by far the best energy values for closed shell atoms⁷. The electrostatic potential $\phi(\mathbf{r})$ for an atom is given by

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{Z}{r} + \int \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}' \quad (5)$$

and it has been shown to be important^{9,10} as its value at the covalent radius (r_c) is equal to μ since at that point,

$$\frac{\delta T}{\delta \rho} + \frac{\delta E_{xc}}{\delta \rho} = 0 \quad (6)$$

In equation (6), T and E_{xc} are kinetic and exchange-correlation energy functionals respectively.

Equation (4) has been solved self-consistently to obtain the density profiles for alkaline earth metal atoms (Ca, Sr and Ba) and their monovalent and mononegative ions. Thereby we have obtained the chemical potentials of these systems as the respective electrostatic potentials at the points where equation (6) is valid. The hardness (η) values for these systems are then calculated by making use of a finite difference approximation¹¹ to the derivative given in equation (2). For example, the hardness of Ca is calculated as

$$\eta_{Ca} \cong \frac{\phi(r_o)_{Ca^-} - \phi(r_o)_{Ca^+}}{2} \quad (7)$$

It may be noted that in equation (7) it has been tacitly assumed that the external potential remains same for all the species with same atomic number, e.g. Ca^- , Ca and Ca^+ .

In order to understand the effect of changing the number of electrons in an atom on its hardness¹² we define the property called colour (β) as

$$\beta = \left(\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial N} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu}{\partial N^2} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} = \left(\frac{\partial^3 E}{\partial N^3} \right)_{\mathbf{v}(r)} \quad (8)$$

It is interesting to note that β may have both the signs and depending on whether it is positive or negative we call the species to be bright- or light-coloured respectively. The colour of any species is calculated as the finite difference analogue of the curvature of the chemical potential with respect to the number of electrons. For example, the colour of Ca is calculated as

$$\beta = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mu}{\partial N^2} \right)_{V(r)} \rightarrow \cong \mu_{Ca^-} - 2\mu_{Ca} + \mu_{Ca^+} \\ = \phi(r_c)_{|Ca^-} - 2\phi(r_c)_{|Ca} + \phi(r_c)_{|Ca^+} \quad (9)$$

As a check, we have calculated the Wigner-Seitz radii¹³ (r_{ws}) of Ca, Sr and Ba. We have also calculated the ionic radii (r_m) of Ca^- , Sr^- and Ba^- where $[-\phi(r_m)]$ is minimum¹⁴. In order to check the following identities for mononegative ions

$$I_1 = \int_0^{r_m} \rho(r) r^2 dr = Z \quad (10a)$$

$$I_2 = 4\pi \int_{r_m}^{\infty} \rho(r) r dr = \phi(r_m) \quad (10b)$$

we have calculated the integrals using Simpson's rule and compared them with the respective values on the right-hand-side of equation (10).

red with the experimental values¹⁶ and the similar quantities calculated by means of a self-interaction corrected DFT including correlation terms¹⁷. Here experimental values refer to the values calculated using the accepted definitions of χ and η and by making use of the experimental values of ionisation potential and electron affinity therein. It is quite gratifying to note that our results compare very well considering the computational simplicity. For systems with same number of protons, χ value decrease with increase in number of electrons eventually becoming negative for the mononegative ions. Therefore, a mononegative ion gets destabilised in case an electron is added to or removed from it. The hardness values from the present calculation follow the same trend, viz. $\eta_{Sr} > \eta_{Ca} > \eta_{Ba}$ as followed by those values obtained by Goycoolea *et al.*¹⁷. Although the experimental η values¹⁶ are comparable to these values, the trend is slightly different mainly because the experimental hardness value¹⁶ of Ca is much larger than the corresponding calculated values. It is interesting to note that equation (11) gives the same η values as corresponding η^{III} values or Ca, Sr and Ba when all quantities on the right-hand side of it are taken from the present calculation. The β values suggest that Ca and Ba are light-coloured atoms while Sr is bright-coloured. Colour deserves a detailed study.

TABLE 1—DIFFERENT RADII, ELECTRONEGATIVITY, HARDNESS AND COLOURS FOR ALKALINE EARTH SYSTEMS (IN a.u)

Atom/ Ion	r_c	r_{ws}	r_m	I_1	I_2	$\phi(r_m)$	χ			η			β	
							Present calcula- tion $\phi(r_c)$	Experi- mental* lit.**	From lit.**	Present calcula- tion	Experi- mental* lit.**	From lit.**		
Ca ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.450 1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ca	2.856 1	2.979 3	—	—	—	—	0.087 5	0.080 8	0.117 6	0.257 6	0.294 0	0.205 8	-0.210 0	—
Ca ⁻	—	—	5.290 0	20.020 4	0.171 9	0.170 0	-0.065 1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sr ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.408 4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Sr	2.890 0	2.936 2	—	—	—	—	0.137 0	0.073 5	0.096 3	0.275 2	0.272 0	0.215 4	0.007 7	—
Sr ⁻	—	—	4.326 4	38.008 6	0.189 0	0.185 7	-0.142 1	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ba ⁺	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.423 2	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Ba	3.132 9	2.884 4	—	—	—	—	0.090 9	0.088 2	0.091 9	0.234 8	0.213 2	0.183 7	-0.195 0	—
Ba ⁻	—	—	5.428 9	56.020 9	0.176 3	0.168 2	-0.046 4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

*Ref. 16. **Ref. 17.

The hardness values have also been calculated using the following five-point finite difference formula¹⁵,

$$\eta^V = (1/6) [8\eta^{III} + \chi^- - \chi^+] \quad (11)$$

where η^{III} is the corresponding three-point finite difference value and χ^+ and χ^- are the electronegativity values of the monopositive and mononegative ions of the atom whose hardness is determined.

Table 1 presents the values of r_c , r_{ws} , r_m , I_1 , I_2 , $\phi(r_m)$, χ , η and β . The χ and η values are com-

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